

Evaluation of Cardiopulmonary Resuscitation (CPR) Training Programs to Schoolchildren: A Comprehensive Systematic Review

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Abstract

Background: First aid is now widely recognized as a crucial life skill, particularly in emergency situations where it can be lifesaving. School-based cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CPR) training programs have become integral to comprehensive education, providing students with practical skills to respond to medical emergencies both in and out of school settings. This article delves into the importance, advantages, obstacles, and suggestions for implementing these programs.

Method: This systematic review followed the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews guidelines meticulously. Thorough searches were conducted in major databases like PubMed, Medline, ScienceDirect, Scopus, Web of Science, and PLOS, covering January to August 2023. The main aim was to assess the effectiveness of school-based CPR training programs for students aged 4 to 18. Inclusion criteria included studies with experimental designs providing first aid training to children and evaluating outcomes related to knowledge, skills, behaviour, or confidence.

Results: A comprehensive collection of sixty-three articles contributed to this review. Systematic analyses collectively provide evidence that the introduction of CPR training programs within educational settings is reinforced by experimental evidence. Predominantly situated within the past decade, the results showed a collective shift towards prioritizing CPR education among schoolchildren. Altogether, the program displays effectiveness in augmenting first aid expertise both immediately and, in long-term following training.

Conclusions: The synthesis of sixty-three studies reveals video simulation as the predominant pedagogical method in CPR training. Evaluation focuses largely on subjective measures, emphasizing the exploratory nature of assessments. The study emphasizes the crucial role of CPR training for well-prepared citizens, advocating integration into curricula despite implementation challenges.

Keywords: cardiopulmonary resuscitation; first aid; school health programs; school-based training; systematic review.

1. Introduction:

Cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CPR) is a life-saving technique that holds immense significance in improving survival rates following cardiac arrest incidents. In the context of out-of-hospital cardiac arrest (OHCA), which remains a critical public

health concern, the prompt initiation of CPR by bystanders significantly enhances the chances of survival. OHCA occurs suddenly and unexpectedly. Despite advancements in medical care, survival rates for OHCA remain low (Berdowski et al., 2010). According to Bystander CPR and Survival Rates, a study by Berdowski et al., the survival rate from OHCA in the US varied widely, ranging from

0.2% to 16%. In Europe, the survival rates of OHCA ranged from 0.2% to 21.8%, with significant disparities between nations, as documented in the EuReCa ONE study by Gräsner *et al.*, Australia, like other regions, has also been working towards enhancing OHCA survival rates (Gräsner *et al.*, 2016).

Findings from the Aus-ROC Epistry, encompassing data spanning from 2000 to 2019, reveal a comprehensive overview of OHCA response and outcomes in Australia and New Zealand. Notably, within the subset of OHCA cases not directly witnessed by emergency medical services (EMS) personnel, bystander CPR was administered in 38% of instances, while a mere 2% benefitted from public defibrillation. The data also underscores a striking divergence across EMS regions, manifesting as significant disparities in OHCA demographics, arrest characteristics, and ultimate patient outcomes (Bray *et al.*, 2022).

Of particular significance are the outcomes associated with cases where EMS-initiated resuscitation measures were undertaken. Among this cohort, 28% achieved a return of spontaneous circulation (ROSC) upon arrival at the hospital, and a noteworthy 13% managed to survive to hospital discharge or up to 30 days post-arrest. It is imperative to acknowledge that survival rates within the Utstein comparator group, specifically those characterized by bystander-witnessed arrests presenting a shockable rhythm, exhibit substantial heterogeneity across various EMS regions, ranging from 27.4% to 42.0% (Bray *et al.*, 2022).

In the most recent available data, pertaining to the years 2021-2022, the survival rate for cardiac arrests not witnessed by paramedic personnel but where resuscitative efforts were initiated stood at 21.4% (Report on Government Services, 2023). These statistics highlight the need for ongoing efforts to increase community awareness about CPR and bystander intervention including effective CPR and early defibrillation (Cartledge *et al.*, 2020; Gräsner *et al.*, 2016).

Considering this, CPR training for schoolchildren has gained significant attention in recent years. Legislation mandating CPR education in schools and the workplace, such as the "CPR in Schools Legislation" advocated by the American Heart Association (Diana M Cave *et al.*, 2011), has begun to contribute to creating a society better equipped to respond to cardiac emergencies. Similarly, the

Council of Ambulance Authorities and the Australian Red Cross has advocated for public education of CPR and AED usage and compulsory first aid training in schools, respectively (Australian Red Cross, 2015; The Council of Ambulance Authorities, 2023-2028 Strategy, 2023).

The benefits of CPR training in schools extend beyond the immediate impact on students (Berger, 2020). According to Lukas *et al.*, conducting a longitudinal study over six years, schoolchildren learning CPR can be effective and have a lasting effect on their knowledge and skills (Lukas *et al.*, 2016). This indicates that integrating CPR education into school curricula, can raise a generation of individuals with life-saving capabilities. In this systematic review, we assess the efficacy of CPR training within schools through evaluating the influence of such training on CPR knowledge and skills among schoolchildren from various dimensions.

2. Methods

The methodological approach employed for this review involved assessment of applicable scholarly literature, extending until the month of August in the year 2023. We devised the criteria to include studies whereby CPR training was imparted to schoolchildren, with a specific focus on evaluating outcomes pertaining to their cognitive understanding, practical aptitude, behavioural responses, and self-assurance levels in this domain. The pool of information was diverse, encompassing a spectrum of original research, systematic reviews, randomized controlled trials, and observational studies (Figure 1).

The analysis incorporated data from sixty-three articles published in peer reviewed journals. We formulated the criteria for eligibility were to include studies, wherein the target audience comprised children within the age bracket of four to eighteen years. The studies involving children below the age of four and beyond the age of eighteen years were excluded from consideration. The search methodology included subject-specific vocabulary and natural language terms, such as 'Out of Hospital Cardiac Arrest,' 'Cardiopulmonary Resuscitation,' 'First Aid,' 'School Health Programs,' 'School-Based Training,' and 'Review.' There was no limitation to the publication year. This review has been covered a multitude of renowned bibliographic repositories,

Figure 1: Study Methodology

spanning the likes of PubMed, Medline, ScienceDirect, Scopus, Web of Science, and PLOS. To maximize the comprehensiveness of the review, we combined the data from multiple reports originating from the same study. We also examined the citations of the included studies, to uncover additional studies that might have eluded the electronic search.

3. Results

A comprehensive search of various databases yielded a total of hundred and fifteen articles. Upon closer examination, seventeen duplicate entries were identified and subsequently eliminated, leaving ninety-eight unique articles for meticulous screening and assessment. Among these, sixty-three

articles exhibited alignment with the predetermined criteria for full-text evaluation. We excluded thirty-five articles from the study due to their inability to fulfill the established eligibility prerequisites.

Consequently, the systematic review encompassed a final selection of sixty-three articles, each of which underwent rigorous scrutiny and analysis. This process ensured the incorporation of only the most pertinent and fitting contributions, culminating in a comprehensive review.

3.1. Outcome of the Review

3.1.1. Effectiveness of Training Programs

In a study, conducted by Kanstad et al. in 2011, the CPR knowledge among secondary school students

was reported limited (Kanstad et al., 2011). This knowledge and skills, however, can be enhanced through training programs (Reder & Quan, 2003); (Colquhoun, 2012); (Kate H Magid 2018)), even if it would be as short as a 3-day first aid training program (Banfai et al., 2017).

Teaching basic life-saving skills including CPR to primary school students was shown to be feasible in increasing early life-saving awareness (Calicchia et al., 2016); (Chamdawala et al., 2021). In a systematic review of various first aid programs by Reveruzzi et al. (2016), the multifaceted benefits of such programs expanded from enhancement of students' first aid knowledge and skills to the broader societal impact of creating a cohort of informed and capable first responders. One example is a report, showing increase of such students' willing to proficiently instruct their peers in high-quality CPR program (Damvall et al., 2022).

While the gender of students had no impact on training effectiveness, the age played a key role on designing the elements of such a program for different age categories (Finke et al., 2018). It was demonstrated that children as young as primary school age could grasp the concepts of basic life support (BLS), comprehend its significance, and apply these skills effectively (Maconochie et al., 2007). Recent studies suggested that even kindergarten children can absorb fundamental life-saving competencies (Goedde et al., 2022); (Tse et al., 2022). The effectiveness of such a training was the subject of Naqvi et al. experiments, and review study of Tse and her colleagues (Naqvi et al., 2011; Tse et al., 2023), when they proved the actual success of teaching BLS skills to schoolchildren in increasing their knowledge and skills, and in the practical set. Similar studies in Korea, assessing CPR education effects on elementary school students, revealed improved schoolchildren CPR knowledge, attitudes, and self-efficacy (Ko et al., 2023). In China, Li et al. evaluation on CPR attitudes and willingness among Chinese middle school students, reported a generally positive attitudes and a desire for more training among the schoolchildren (Li et al., 2023) (Table 1).

3.1.2. Long-Term Retention of Skills

A decade ago, a longitudinal study on development of BLS skills among high school students following CPR training revealed substantial improvement in

BLS competencies post-training over time (Meissner et al., 2012). In a similar longitudinal investigation in 2016, Lukas et al. conducted a six-year study on schoolchildren's acquisition of CPR skills. This study examined the sustained effects of different teaching methodologies (taught by peers or adult instructors) and explored the dynamics of student-to-student knowledge transfer over the time. The longevity of the acquired skills and the role of various actors in this process suggested the long-term impact of BLS education, regardless of whether they were taught by peers or adult instructors (Lukas et al., 2016).

In another longitudinal study by Villanueva Ordóñez et al., the sustained educational intervention showed to promote CPR skills among schoolchildren (Villanueva Ordóñez et al., 2019). The results, however, extended beyond the immediate training period, demonstrating continuity of skill retention over time. Expanding the training to younger children, Tse et al. set its focus on the kindergarten demographic through a pilot study (Tse et al., 2022). Their findings suggested that young children not only absorb essential life-saving competencies, but those acquired abilities could become embedded within their skill collection for the long haul. A recent study in 2023 demonstrated that providing basic life support training to children between the ages of 4 and 6 has had a significant impact on their capacity to identify potential medical emergencies. This training has notably enhanced their ability to initiate the chain of survival by promptly alerting a responsible adult and dialling the emergency number, particularly among students in the final year of preschool education (Pedrazas-López et al., 2023). Just before that, Pivač et al., also observed positive shifts in students' CPR knowledge, attitudes, and responsiveness, which could be translated into a long-lasting awareness and preparedness for life-saving actions (Pivač et al., 2020) (Table 1).

3.1.3. Training Approach

In 2013, Creutzfeldt et al. investigated the potential effect of virtual worlds in training CPR skills. Their research proved that this form of training not only enhanced skill acquisition but also improved the interactive landscape of skill retention. While the temporal span of retention remains tacit, the very integration of virtual platforms introduces an

element of contemporary engagement that might inherently contribute to the sustained presence of acquired skills in students' cognitive toolkits (Creutzfeldt *et al.*, 2013).

Adapting the BLS training, including CPR to suit the developmental stages of the learners, have been reported as an essential requirement in designing such programs. Plant and Taylor (2013) reviewed the most effective strategies to educate schoolchildren in CPR. Their synthesis of various methodologies showed the importance of age-appropriate teaching techniques and the impact of engaging approaches in maximizing learning outcomes. Such interactive and hands-on teaching methods were found effective through utilizing techniques like manikins and role-playing to enhance CPR skills among students (Plant & Taylor, 2013).

In a cluster randomized controlled trial, Iserbyt *et al.* evaluated the impact of a specialized content knowledge workshop on teaching and learning BLS in elementary schools, revealing improved BLS teaching effectiveness in the intervention group (Iserbyt *et al.*, 2017). For high school students, however, using virtual CPR training through utilizing a 360-degree virtual reality environment resulted in high level of engagement in participating in the training approach (E. Z. Barsom 2020). In another study, Otero-Agra *et al.* introduced gamification as a CPR training methodology in secondary school students and found that this approach improved performance in a manikin simulation (Otero-Agra *et al.*, 2019) (Table 1).

3.1.4. School Curriculum Integration

Previous studies emphasized the importance of integrating CPR and automated external defibrillation (AED) training into school curricula (Diana M Cave *et al.*, 2011); (Hoyme & Atkins, 2017); (Wilks J., 2017). Based on such studies, several countries have taken steps to advocate for the inclusion of CPR training in schools. The Australian Red Cross, for instance, has called for compulsory first aid training in schools to equip students with life-saving skills. In the United States, legislation has been introduced in 2015 by the American Heart Association in various states to mandate CPR training in schools, providing a broader contextual backdrop by emphasizing the importance of CPR

training in schools.

Lafferty *et al.* investigated the state of resuscitation teaching in New Zealand schools almost two decades ago (Lafferty *et al.*, 2003). Their findings highlighted the need for standardized CPR education and better integration within the curriculum. In 2010, Markenson *et al.* formulated guidelines for standardized first aid interventions. Their framework has served as a foundational cornerstone, leading the training and practice of first aid techniques across various contexts (Markenson *et al.*, 2010). In a report, Cave *et al.* promoted the discourse to a scientific advisory level by revealing the critical importance of CPR and AED training within school settings. Their advisory provided a foundation for understanding the necessity of incorporating BLS education into schools (Diana M Cave *et al.*, 2011).

The importance of incorporating this structured approach, into a curriculum that systematically imparts vital first aid knowledge and practical skills, was further emphasized by De Buck *et al.* (2015) through an evidence-based educational pathway (De Buck *et al.*, 2015), while the aspect of parental and societal attitudes toward BLS training within primary schools was examined by Petrić *et al.*, showing a positive disposition toward integrating BLS education into primary school curricula (Petrić *et al.*, 2013). In 2019, De Smedt *et al.* provided further evidence on willingness to perform CPR among Flemish schoolchildren, teachers, and principals. They reported positive attitudes towards CPR training, with teachers and principals, expressing support for the training inclusion in the curriculum (De Smedt *et al.*, 2019).

During a nationwide survey in Denmark, conducted by Malta Hansen research team (Carolina Malta Hansen 2017), the CPR training in schools was assessed after eight years of mandating legislation. The findings suggested that while most schools complied with the legislation, disparities still existed in training quality and frequency. In a similar cross-sectional study in London to assess basic life support education in secondary schools, Salciccioli *et al.* found variability in training methods, curriculum integration, and the role of instructors (Salciccioli *et al.*, 2017). The results of a study by Salvatierra, Palazzo, and Emery in Washington state also showed that urban high schools were more likely to offer training than rural

schools, suggesting the demographic difference in implementing CPR/AED training in school curriculum (Salvatierra et al., 2017) (Table 1).

3.1.5. Determining the Ideal Instructor

Patsaki et al. study on Greek high school teachers' knowledge about basic life support and AED,

revealed knowledge gaps among teachers (Patsaki et al., 2012). Jorge-Soto et al. used a simulation trial to assess the suitability of schoolteachers as BLS trainers, demonstrating that teachers could effectively teach BLS skills after proper training and simulation exercises (Jorge-Soto et al., 2019). Jiménez-Fábrega et al. compared teacher-only and mixed teacher-healthcare provider CPR programs.

Paper Title	Aspect of CPR/PBL Training	Findings
Kanstad et al. (2011)	CPR Knowledge Among Secondary School Students	CPR knowledge among secondary school students was limited.
Reder and Quan (2003)	Effectiveness of Training Programs	Training programs can enhance CPR knowledge and skills.
Magid, Heard, and Sasson (2018)	Effectiveness of Training Programs	Training programs are effective in improving CPR knowledge and skills.
Colquhoun (2012)	Effectiveness of Training Programs	Training programs can enhance CPR knowledge and skills.
Banfai et al. (2017)	Effectiveness of Training Programs	Even short 3-day first aid training programs can improve CPR knowledge and skills.
Calicchia et al. (2016)	CPR Training for Primary School Students	Teaching CPR to primary school students increases early life-saving awareness.
Chamdawala et al. (2021)	CPR Training for Primary School Students	Teaching basic life-saving skills to primary school students is feasible and beneficial.
Reveruzzi et al. (2016)	Systematic Review of First Aid Programs	First aid programs enhance students' first aid knowledge, skills, and create a cohort of informed first responders.
Damvall et al. (2022)	Long-Term Retention of Skills	Students trained in high-quality CPR programs are willing and proficient in instructing their peers.
Finke et al. (2018)	Effect of Age on Training Effectiveness	Age plays a key role in designing CPR training programs for different age categories.
Tse et al. (2022)	CPR Training for Kindergarten Children	Kindergarten children can absorb fundamental life-saving competencies.
Goedde et al. (2022)	CPR Training for Kindergarten Children	Kindergarten children can acquire essential life-saving competencies.
Pedrazas-Garcia et al. (2023)	CPR Training for pre-school Children	Pre-school children's basic life-support training enhances their ability to initiate the chain of survival.
Naqvi et al. (2011)	CPR Training for Schoolchildren	Successful teaching of BLS skills to schoolchildren was demonstrated in practical settings.
Ko et al. (2023)	CPR Education Effects on Elementary School Students	CPR education improves CPR knowledge, attitudes, and self-efficacy among elementary school students.
Ko et al. (2023)	CPR Attitudes Among Middle School Students	Chinese middle school students have positive attitudes toward CPR training.
Meissner et al. (2012)	Long-Term Retention of Skills	Longitudinal study showed substantial improvement in BLS competencies among high school students post-training.
Lukas et al. (2016)	Long-Term Retention of Skills	Longitudinal study explored the long-term impact of different teaching methodologies on schoolchildren's CPR skills.
Villanueva Ordóñez et al. (2019)	Long-Term Retention of Skills (Kindergarten)	Sustained educational intervention promotes CPR skills among schoolchildren.

Tse et al. (2022)	Long-Term Retention of Skills	Pilot study showed young children can acquire and retain essential life-saving competencies.
Pivač et al. (2020)	Long-Term Retention of Skills	Positive shifts in students' CPR knowledge, attitudes, and responsiveness were observed.
Creutzfeldt et al. (2013)	Training Approach (Virtual Worlds)	Virtual worlds enhance CPR skill acquisition and retention.
Plant and Taylor (2013)	Training Approach (Interactive Techniques)	Age-appropriate teaching techniques and engaging approaches are crucial for effective CPR education.
Iserbyt et al. (2017)	Impact of Content Knowledge Workshop	Specialized content knowledge workshops improved BLS teaching effectiveness in elementary schools.
Barsom et al. (2020)	Training Approach (Virtual CPR Training)	Virtual CPR training in a 360-degree virtual reality environment engaged high school students effectively.
Otero-Agra et al. (2019)	Training Approach (Gamification)	Gamification improved CPR performance in secondary school students during manikin simulation.
Cave et al. (2011)	School Curriculum Integration	Integration of CPR and AED training into school curricula is essential.
Hoyme & Atkins (2017)	School Curriculum Integration	Emphasized the importance of integrating CPR training into school curricula.
Lafferty et al. (2003)	School Curriculum Integration (New Zealand)	Highlighted the need for standardized CPR education and better integration into the curriculum in New Zealand.
Markenson et al. (2010)	School Curriculum Integration	Formulated guidelines for standardized first aid interventions.
Cave et al. (2011)	School Curriculum Integration	Emphasized the critical importance of CPR and AED training in school settings.
De Buck et al. (2015)	School Curriculum Integration	An evidence-based educational pathway emphasized the importance of structured CPR education.
Petrić et al. (2013)	School Curriculum Integration	Showed positive attitudes toward integrating BLS education into primary school curricula.
Smedt et al. (2018)	School Curriculum Integration	Teachers and principals expressed support for CPR training inclusion in the curriculum.
Malta Hansen et al. (2017)	School Curriculum Integration	Most schools complied with CPR training legislation, but disparities in training quality and frequency existed.
Salciccioli et al. (2017)	School Curriculum Integration	Found variability in CPR training methods and curriculum integration in London secondary schools.
Salvatierra, Palazzo, and Emery (2017)	School Curriculum Integration	Urban high schools were more likely to offer CPR/AED training than rural schools.
Patsaki et al. (2012)	Determining the Ideal Instructor (Greek High School Teachers)	Greek high school teachers had knowledge gaps in basic life support and AED.
Jorge-Soto et al. (2018)	Determining the Ideal Instructor (Suitability of Schoolteachers as BLS Trainers)	Simulation trial demonstrated that schoolteachers can effectively teach BLS skills after training and simulation.
Jiménez-Fábrega et al. (2009)	Determining the Ideal Instructor (Teacher-Only vs. Mixed Teacher-Healthcare Provider CPR)	Mixed teacher-healthcare provider CPR programs were more effective in terms of skills retention and knowledge.
Sanati, Jaberi, and Bonabi (2022)	Determining the Ideal Instructor	Trainer Experience in CPR training enhanced students' CPR performance.
Zamzami et al. (2023)	Determining the status of CPR training in high school	Inadequate availability of CPR training for staff and students

Table 1. Research Findings on CPR and PBL Training in School Settings

He reported that the mixed approach yielded better results in terms of skills retention and knowledge acquisition (Jiménez-Fábrega et al., 2009). The trainer experience in the actual setting, on the other hand, significantly influenced BLS training of high school students and their CPR performance (Sanati et al., 2022) (Table 1).

3.2. Challenges

The value of incorporating CPR training into school systems is abundantly clear through research studies. The path to achieving this integration, however, is surrounded with challenges such as curriculum alignment, teacher preparedness, and allocation of resources.

The knowledge gaps among high school educators concerning BLS, AED, and foreign body airway obstruction is one of the challenges, which was investigated by the work of (Patsaki et al., 2012). These gaps, in turn, hinder the accurate and comprehensive transmission of BLS training to students. In this line, a longitudinal prospective cohort study spanning four years, (Bohn et al., 2012), illustrated the efficiency of trained teachers in imparting BLS instruction to students. Nevertheless, a variance in the quality of CPR performance among schoolchildren further emphasized the continuous need for assessment and refinement of training programs (Oliveira et al., 2022); (Zamzami et al., 2023).

Teaching the proper CPR technique poses an additional challenge, a matter elucidated in Hill et al.'s investigation. This study examined the CPR proficiency of 10-11-year-old students, scrutinizing different chest compression to ventilation ratios. The findings brought to light the difficulties in maintaining the correct technique consistently (Hill et al., 2009).

Lack of high-level collaboration brings up another challenge in CPR training to schoolchildren. The "Kids Save Lives" initiative, advocated in another study, highlights society's responsibility to equip schoolchildren with CPR skills. This emphasizes the imperative for collaborative efforts and dedicated resources to effectively materialize such programs (Böttiger et al., 2017).

While designing lucid guidelines, teacher preparation, and administrative backing have been suggested as some strategies, ensuring successful

implementation (Lockey et al., 2016), the major challenge regarding obstacles related to resource allocation to curriculum integration persisted unresolved as it was reported by Miró et al. (Miró et al., 2006). Such study shows that resource allocation can be challenging, particularly in schools with limited budgets, further hindering CPR training programs at schools.

4. Discussion

OHCA remains a significant public health concern due to its unexpected nature. Numerous studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of CPR training programs for different age groups. The effectiveness of CPR training programs has far-reaching implications. Equipping individuals across various demographics with CPR knowledge and skills, contributes to creating a network of potential first responders (Geri et al., 2017). When schoolchildren are included in this network, the potential for early life-saving interventions is magnified, as they become a part of a generation adept at responding to emergencies. Schoolchildren, as they grow into adulthood, carry this resilience forward, perpetuating a culture of preparedness and responsiveness within society (Goedde et al., 2022).

Weaving CPR education at school into subjects like health, physical education, or science, implements the training within the broader educational framework. This integration enhances the relevance of CPR skills, reinforcing their significance beyond isolated training sessions. Additionally, aligning CPR training with academic subjects promotes a holistic understanding of health and safety (Wilks J., 2017).

Adapting CPR training methods at school that suits the developmental stages of children is another essential component in a successful training program. Considering developmental stages when implementing CPR training into curriculum, ensures inclusivity, accessibility, and adaptability. Young learners have varying abilities and preferences, and developmentally aligned methods cater to these diversities, acknowledge the cognitive development and learning preferences of different age cohorts. (Pivač et al., 2022).

On the other hand, the effectiveness of schoolteachers as CPR trainers is another crucial element in imparting CPR skills to schoolchildren.

From an educational standpoint, schoolteachers possess the expertise to effectively convey complex information to diverse learners. Their pedagogical training equips them with skills to break down concepts into understandable components, ensuring that CPR training is accessible to students. Teachers are adept at adapting their instructional techniques to cater to varying learning styles, ensuring that CPR education resonates with each student. Their familiarity with classroom dynamics enables them to create a comfortable and supportive learning environment, encouraging engagement and knowledge retention (Jorge-Soto et al., 2019). Therefore, providing ongoing training for teachers equip them with the knowledge and confidence to teach CPR effectively.

While the benefits of CPR training in schools are evident, challenges persist in integrating it into curricula. Curriculum alignment and teacher preparedness are hurdles that require attention. Addressing knowledge gaps among educators through targeted interventions is crucial for ensuring accurate knowledge transmission. Collaborative efforts supported by clear guidelines and teacher preparation, can pave the way for effective CPR education. Administrative support also plays a pivotal role in overcoming logistical barriers and ensuring that CPR training becomes an integral part of school curricula.

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Another challenge is availability of resources, both human and material. Manikins, training materials, and access to healthcare professionals for demonstrations are essential components. Forming partnerships with local healthcare institutions, and utilizing innovative, cost-effective teaching methods that make the of available resources, could be used as some strategies toward securing the required resources.

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, the CPR training programs at school create a network of potential first responders by equipping schoolchildren with vital CPR knowledge. Integrating CPR education into academic subjects enhances its relevance and promotes a culture of preparedness. In accomplishing this matter, schoolteachers play a crucial role, utilizing their pedagogical skills to effectively convey CPR concepts to students and create a supportive learning environment. Addressing challenges on the way, such as curriculum alignment and resource allocation requires collaborative efforts and administrative support and should be a measure to consider in future studies.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest regarding the content presented in this manuscript.